

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Training Platform, Work Package 3 -
Consolidating ELIXIR Training standards and best practices
for Open science and Open education

M3.7 Available in the Training SPLASH, a FAIR training material checklist based on the FAIR training handbook checklist

Tier: Technology

Executive Summary

Making training materials FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) comes with many advantages, both for trainers and trainees. However, making training materials FAIR can be overwhelming. In order to understand what is already in place and still needs to be done for (a set of) training materials to align with the FAIR principles, the FAIR training Focus Group has created a checklist of the most important indicators, and published it as part of the FAIR Training Handbook. This checklist went through several rounds of review, within the FAIR training Focus Group and outside (among which during a session of the Global Bioinformatics Education Summit in 2024), and has now been explicitly linked in the FAIR Training Handbook page on SPLASH.

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Supporting Documents

The checklist in the FAIR training handbook:

<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-FAIR-training-handbook/checklist/>

The chapter on the SPLASH website in which the checklist is linked:

<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/fair-training-handbook#what-can-you-do-with-fair-training-handbook>

Presentation at GBES 2024: fair_training_GBES

Feedback summary GBES 2024: feedback_summary_FAIR_checklist_GBES

Dissemination Plans

The FAIR Training Handbook is published as a [website](#) and on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/10839551>. The Handbook, including its checklist, has been actively promoted at its release in March '24. As part of this milestone it is explicitly linked on the [SPLASH website](#).